

God, Teacher, Nation and the Importance of Transcendental Jurisdiction to Quran

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Accepted and published July, 2024

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Abstract:

We try to elaborate the importance of transcendental jurisdiction to Quran in order to determine the hermeneutics and the language of Quran. Without such jurisdiction a vague gap of darkness implying the platonic realm of ignorance rises in the Islamic nations which causes chaos and distractions. We also try resolve the linguistics of the resurrection of teacher in Quran and answer allegory of David in Quran and the question of existence of Israel prophesized by a philosophical question in Quran and determine the platonic state of ignorance caused in Islamic nations by unawareness of the transcendental truth and hermeneutics within Quran.

Keywords: Allegory of David, Consciousness

The Value of Honor to Wisdom: A Philosophical Reflection

King and Teacher's legacy:

In the annals of history, we often find contrasting lives that provoke deep contemplation about the nature of honor and wisdom. One such contemplation arises from the tale of a king and a teacher, presenting us with profound questions about the essence of life and the true foundation of the world.

The king, a figure of immense power and authority, killed thousands and ruled with an iron fist. His reign was marked by judgments and flourishing prosperity, and upon his death, he was lauded by all, even his enemies. His legacy was one of strength and dominance, earning him widespread acclaim and respect.

In stark contrast, the teacher lived a life of poverty and asceticism. For a hundred years, he taught and learned, fasting frequently and abstaining from worldly pleasures. Despite his dedication to knowledge and spiritual practice, he garnered neither respect from his relatives and companions nor accumulated any wealth. When he passed away, his name was forgotten, unmentioned by those he had impacted.

Witnessing these contrasting fates, a judge pondered deeply, asking both himself and God: "Who deserves honor? And what is the value of knowledge and wisdom?" This question underscores the perplexing nature of human recognition and the inherent value of intellectual and spiritual pursuits.

In this contemplation, the judge draws a comparison between the teacher and the ruler, questioning the very foundation of the world and the essence of honor. To delve deeper, we turn to the philosophical insights of Plato and the teachings of the Quran.

Plato's Duality of Existence

Plato's philosophy speaks of a duality in existence, dividing the world into the realm of truth and the realm of appearances. The world of truth, or the world of forms, is where the essence of events unfolds. This concept is exemplified in various sacred texts and teachings.

Quranic Insights

Surah Al-Jumu'ah, Verse 2, states:

"هُوَ الَّذِي بَعَثَ فِي الْأُمِّيِّينَ رَسُولًا مِنْهُمْ يَتْلُو عَلَيْهِمْ آيَاتِهِ وَيُزَكِّيهِمْ وَيُعَلِّمُهُمُ الْكِتَابَ وَالْحِكْمَةَ وَإِنْ كَانُوا مِنْ قَبْلُ لَفِي ضَلَالٍ مُبِينٍ"

"He is the One who sent among the unlettered a Messenger from themselves, reciting to them His verses, purifying them, and teaching them the Book and wisdom, although they were in clear error before."

The word "بعث" reflects a state of resurrection "در فارسی رستاخیز" and has been used by the governments in Iran, Iraq and Syria to determine revolutionary actions during Pahlavi dynasty and Saddam Hussain and still is ruling in Syria with Baas party of Bashar al-Asad.

This verse highlights the importance of teaching and purification in the realm of truth. It aligns with Plato's allegory of the cave, where individuals in darkness (error) cannot grasp the truth unless someone enlightened exits the cave and returns to guide them.

The Linguistic and Philosophical Roots of "بعث"

The Arabic word "بعث" (ba'ath) holds deep connotations of resurrection, awakening, and revival. In linguistic and philosophical terms, "بعث" signifies a state of bringing something back to life or initiating a new beginning from a dormant or suppressed state. This concept is not only relevant in religious and cultural contexts but also finds significant application in political ideologies and movements.

Political Utilization in the Middle East

In the 20th and 21st centuries, the concept of "بعث" and its Persian analogue "رستاخیز" were appropriated by political movements in several Middle Eastern countries, notably Iran, Iraq, and Syria, to signify revolutionary actions and ideological transformations. This term became particularly prominent during the regimes of the Pahlavi dynasty in Iran, Saddam Hussein in Iraq, and the ongoing governance of Bashar al-Assad in Syria.

During the Pahlavi dynasty (1925-1979), the notion of "بعث" was embodied in efforts to modernize and secularize Iran. The dynasty sought to resurrect Persian nationalism and cultural identity,

transforming Iran into a contemporary nation-state. This process involved extensive social, economic, and political reforms aimed at reviving the country's historical legacy and integrating it into the modern world.

In Iraq, the Ba'ath Party, led by Saddam Hussein, explicitly adopted the term "بعث" to denote its revolutionary ideology. Founded in 1947, the Ba'ath Party aimed to achieve Arab unity and socialism through radical transformation. The party's name itself, Hizb al-Ba'ath al-Arabi al-Ishtiraki (Arab Socialist Ba'ath Party), reflects this ideology of resurrection and renewal. Under Saddam Hussein's rule (1979-2003), Iraq underwent significant political and social changes, often characterized by authoritarianism and aggressive nationalism.

Similarly, in Syria, the Ba'ath Party has been a dominant force since the 1960s. Bashar al-Assad's regime continues to rule under the Ba'athist ideology, promoting a blend of Arab nationalism, socialism, and secularism. The term "بعث" in this context represents the ongoing efforts to maintain and revitalize the nation's identity and political structure amidst internal and external challenges.

The Journey Toward Enlightenment

The behavior of cave dwellers—repetition, resistance, or fear—parallels the human condition in the face of truth. True enlightenment requires a vertical ascent in life, moving beyond mere day-to-day existence. Historical and mythical figures like Khidr, Gilgamesh, Aeneas, Perseus, and Dante exemplify this quest for enlightenment.

Sacred texts, including the Quran, hold the essence of many concepts and values. Their true understanding necessitates enlightenment, a journey from darkness to light. This raises the question: Should the Quran have been revealed, considering the state of error in which it was received?

The Allegory of David in Quran

﴿اصْبِرْ عَلٰی مَا يَقُولُوْنَ وَ اذْكُرْ عِبْدَنَا دَاوُدَ ذَا الْاَيْدِ اِنَّهُ اَوَّابٌ (17) اِنَّا سَخَّرْنَا الْجِبَالَ مَعَهُ يُسَبِّحْنَ بِالْعُثْبِيِّ وَ الْاَشْرَاقِ (18) وَ الطَّيْرَ مَخْشُوْرَةً كُلٌّ لِّهٗ اَوَّابٌ (19) وَ سَدَدْنَا مُلْكَهُ وَ اَتَيْنَاهُ الْحِكْمَةَ وَ فَصَّلَ الْخُطَابِ (20) وَ هَلْ اَتَاكَ نَبَاُ الْخَصْمِ اِذْ تَسُوْرُوْا الْمُحْرَابَ (21) اِذْ

دَخَلُوا عَلَي دَاوُدَ فَفَزِعَ مِنْهُمْ قَالُوا لَا تَحْفَ خَصْمَانِ بَغِي بَعْضُنَا عَلَي بَعْضٍ فَاذْكُم بَيْنِنَا بِالْحَقِّ وَ لَا تُشْطِطْ وَ اِهْدِنَا اِلَي سَوَاءِ الصِّرَاطِ (22) اِنَّ هَذَا اَخِي لَهُ تَسْعٌ وَ تِسْعُونَ نَعْجَةً وَ لِي نَعْجَةٌ وَ اِحِدَةٌ فَقَالَ اَكْفُلْنِيهَا وَ عَزَّنِي فِي الْخِطَابِ (23) قَالَ لَقَدْ ظَلَمَكَ بِسُؤَالِ نَعْتِكَ اِلَي نِعَاجِهِ وَ اِنَّ كَثِيْرًا مِّنَ الْخُلَطَاءِ لَيَبْغِي بَعْضُهُمْ عَلَي بَعْضٍ اِلَّا الَّذِيْنَ اٰمَنُوْا وَ عَمِلُوْا (24) الصَّالِحَاتِ وَ قَلِيْلٌ مَّا هُمْ وَ ظَنَّ دَاوُدُ اَنَّمَا فَتَنَّاهُ فَاسْتَغْفَرَ رَبَّهُ وَ خَرَّ رَاكِعًا وَ اٰنَابَ

The allegory of David in Surah Sad (Verses 17 to 24) illustrates a profound lesson. Angels question whether a sheep should be given to an angel who already has many sheep's. The lesson lies not in the literal interpretation but in the elevation of intellect and understanding of justice and wisdom which comes to truth thousands of years later, and questions whether the Israel has the right to be a single vessel within many vessels in the Islamic world.

Conclusion

The contemplation of the judge—reflecting on the lives of the king and the teacher—leads us to profound philosophical and spiritual insights. It challenges us to reconsider the foundations of honor and wisdom, urging us to seek true enlightenment and recognize the essential role of enlightened teachers in our journey toward understanding.

Such understanding of the esoteric Quran “has even a greater impact on the the popular slogan of the Monarchism “God, King, Nation” and transforms it to a different realm, the realm of wisdom and education. God, the teacher, the nation.

Deep and at the same time hermeneutics in Quran marks it dark and untouchable without a transcendental knowledge, and the Quran itself admits to such darkness "لَا يَمَسُّهُ اِلَّا الْمُطَهَّرُوْنَ فِي كِتَابٍ مَّكْنُوْنٍ" (Al-Waqi'ah: 78-79) making it vague and untouchable for those without jurisdiction to Quran, be it the spiritual leaders or normal people who have not been enlightened. The essence of the Quran lies in its layers of enlightenment and darkness, guiding those who seek true understanding.